

strand of several oocytes. At the apex of each ovariole is a syncytium of nurse cells (tropharium) that connect previtellogenic oocytes by strands of cytoplasm (trophicards).

We homogenized mature oocytes in ovaries in a microhomogenizer containing 1.0 ml of 80% ethanol. Chromatogram run in butanol, acetic acid, and water (12:3:5) were localized using 0.2% ninhydrin. Protein content was estimated at different stages of ovary development.

Protein from mature oocytes in the ovary was immunized in a rabbit. One ml sample from the homogenized mixture and an equal volume of complete adjuvant (Sigma) were used for primary injection. Two subsequent booster doses of incomplete adjuvant (Sigma) were given at 10-d intervals. Ouchterlony's immunodiffusion method was followed. Ten microliters of the serum and sample was applied as well. Precipitated proteins

were washed in phosphate saline buffer (pH 7, 0.01 M), dried, and stained in coomassie brilliant blue R-250 (methanol, acetic acid, and water 18:7.5:48.5).

Amino acids increased as ovary growth advanced. In immature and premature ovaries, free amino acid content was, respectively, 39% and 72.25% that of the mature ovary. The increase in amino acids at all stages was statistically significant.

Protein content also increased as the ovary matured. The immature ovary had a minimum value of 17.1% protein, and the premature ovary, 44.4%, that of the fully mature ovary. Protein increase at all stages was significant.

Chromatographic study showed seven free amino acids in the mature ovary: glutamic acid, alanine, hydroxy proline, tyrosine, methionine, tryptophan, and leucine (Fig. 1).

The immunodiffusion study showed

2. Immunodiffusion of ovarian proteins against the antiserum raised in the rabbit.

antivitellin for vitellin of BPH. Two bands were observed after staining in coomassie brilliant blue. Further study is under way to elucidate the role of lytic enzymes in yolk utilization during embryogenesis (Fig. 2). ■

Integrated pest management — weeds

Preliminary study on weed control in dry seeded rice (DSR) after winter wheat

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In DSR, ungerminated rice seeds are broadcast in fields that have been prepared dry; seeded fields are kept wet by interim irrigation. In Henan, DSR is planted in Jun, following winter wheat.

Weeds are a major factor limiting yield. In 1988, we evaluated 11 weeding method and weeding time combinations (see table).

Weeds affected DSR growth and yield mainly through lower numbers of panicles, seed setting, 1,000-grain weight, and panicle length: correlation coefficients with grain yield were highly significant (0.9383, 0.9243, 0.9180, and 0.8880, respectively).

Total accumulated weed weight (X_1) and grasses weight (X_2) correlated negatively with rice grain yield (Y).

Simulated equations were

$$Y(t/ha) = 4.6221 - 0.0068X_1 \text{ (g/m}^2\text{)} \\ (r = 0.9271^{**})$$

$$Y(t/ha) = 4.0561 - 0.0072X_2 \text{ (g/m}^2\text{)} \\ (r = 0.9762^{**})$$

We suggest total weed weight or grasses weight be used as a criterion for assessing crop losses caused by weeds (the higher the weed weight, the lower the rice yield).

Effect of weeding times and methods on weed growth and yield of DSR Yujing 2.^a Zhengzhou, Henan, China, 1988.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (kg/20 m ²)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Seed set (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Weed weight ^d (g/m ²)
Unweeded check	0 d	0	—	—	—	611.53
Weed-free	7.9 a	380.85	94.20	27.53	16.36	343.42
Hoeing 2 WAS + hand weeding 5 WAS	5.6 bc	254.10	92.19	26.41	15.90	318.82
Hoeing 3 WAS + hand weeding 5 WAS	5.2 c	272.40	90.77	26.80	16.20	520.55
Hoeing 3 WAS	1.3 d	137.55	77.79	24.38	15.23	226.29
Hoeing 3 WAS + hand weeding 5 and 7 WAS	7.0 ab	354.15	94.10	27.18	16.44	257.84
Nitrofen + hoeing 3 WAS	6.6 abc	274.95	92.06	26.70	16.32	189.34
Nitrofen + hoeing 3 WAS + hand weeding 5 WAS	6.2 abc	289.20	92.01	27.57	16.55	180.19
Weed-free 10.25 DAS	5.8 bc	272.55	93.04	27.11	16.23	174.73
Weed-free 25-40 DAS	7.6 a	333.30	92.49	27.27	16.27	376.34
Weed-free 40-55 DAS	5.1 c	214.20	91.19	2.5.89	15.90	

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bWAS = weeks after sowing, DAS = days after sowing. ^cMeans followed by a common letter are significantly different at the 5% level by LSD. Total accumulated dry weed weight at each weeding time and harvest individually.

In number of weeds in DSR, broadleaf weeds > grasses > sedges; in weed weight, grasses > broadleaf weeds > sedges. Weed weights correlated closely with rice yield, and integrated analysis indicated that grasses were the most severe problem and the predominant weed species, in spite of lower density.

The major weeds found in association with DSR and their relative density (RD)

and relative dry weight (RDW) were: grasses—*Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Eleusine indica*, and *Digitaria sanguinalis* (RD = 29.58%, RDW = 66.83%); broadleaf weeds—*Rorippa islandica* and *Portulaca oleracea* (RD = 62.75%, RDW = 25.63%); and sedges—*Cyperus rotundus* and *C. difformis* (RD = 7.67%, RDW = 7.54%).

Weeds injured the rice crop most severely 25-40 d after sowing.

Weed control recommendations for DSR farmers are to maintain the crop weed-free during the critical period; or to apply nitrofen immediately after sowing, before weed and rice seedlings emerge, then hoe weeds once within 3 wk after sowing; or hoe within 3 wk of sowing and hand weed 5 and 7 wk after sowing. ■

Integrated pest management — other pests

Comparing arthropod diversity in rice ecosystems

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Diversity reflects two common components: species richness (the number of species in a community) and species evenness or equitability. Diversity indices attempt to combine both components.

We obtained arthropod samples from five rice cultivar IR8866 cultivation sites at weekly intervals from the vegetative stage to panicle initiation. A mylar enclosure 0.5 × 0.5 × 1 m trapped all arthropods on 9 hills each.

The arthropods were sucked up using the FARMCOP suction device. Ten samples from each site were taken weekly, for a total of 540 samples. The arthropods in each sample were identified, counted, and diversity indices computed.

We used Hill's diversity numbers to describe the relationship between indices. These numbers are

Table 1. Mean values of species diversity indices for 5 rice cultivation sites in the Philippines, 1989.

Site	Mean values of diversity indices			
	N ₀	N ₁	N ₂	E ₅
Banaue	8.52	5.70	4.85	0.86
Kiangan	16.77	10.08	7.32	0.70
Bayombong	20.41	10.65	7.07	0.62
Cabanatuan	15.90	4.70	2.82	0.52
IRRI, Los Baños	30.66	12.75	8.09	0.58
LSD	2.69	1.24	0.55	0.051
F	86.8	70.2	28.5	60.6
	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
(%)	45.8	43.7	28.0	23.7

Table 2. Relative abundance of the most common arthropod species for 5 rice cultivation sites in the Philippines, 1989.

Arthropod species	Relative abundance ^a (%) in				
	Banaue	Kiangan	Bayombong	Cabanatuan	IRRI
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	12.6 ²	2.4 ⁸	8.2 ²	21.0 ²	8.9 ⁴
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	3.2	0.5	1.7	3.7 ³	1.8 ⁹
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	2.0	1.6 ¹⁰	2.6 ⁸	1.4	4.7 ⁷
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	5.9 ³	0.1	2.5 ⁹	3.5 ⁴	8.7 ⁵
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	3.3	4.8 ⁵	4.3 ⁵	2.2 ⁶	0.5
<i>Microvelia atrolineata</i>	3.3	10.9 ²	23.1 ¹	49.5 ¹	15.6 ²
<i>Mesovelia vittigera</i>	4.6 ⁵	1.8 ⁹	2.9 ⁷	0.1	1.1 ¹¹
<i>Micronecta</i> sp. 1	4.0 ⁶	0	2.1 ¹⁰	0.4	1.7 ¹⁰
<i>Micraspis</i> sp. 1	2.8	3.4 ⁷	1.9	1.5	0.2
<i>Chironomus</i> sp. 1	7.6 ⁴	7.2 ³	4.4 ⁴	0.8	16.7 ¹
<i>Smithurus</i> sp. 1	24.1 ¹	30.8 ¹	0	0	11.9 ³
Entomobryinid sp. 1	0.1	0	0	0	0.1
Staphylinidae sp. 1	0	0.1	4.9 ³	0	0
<i>Hydrellia philippina</i>	1.5	4.4 ⁶	0.5	0.5	0.1
<i>Pandosa</i> (= <i>Lycosa</i>) <i>pseudoannulata</i>	2.7	5.3 ⁴	3.1 ⁶	2.1	2.9 ⁸
<i>Tetragnatha maxillosa</i>	0.6	2.1	1.7	0.7	2.9 ⁸
<i>Atypena</i> (= <i>Callitrichia</i>) <i>formosana</i>	0.3	1.1	2.9 ⁷	2.3 ⁵	5.5 ⁶
Very abundant species (no.)	5	7	7	3	8
Abundant species (no.)	6	10	11	5	12
% contribution of abundant species	58.8	73.1	60.0	80.0	82.4
Total arthropods, N	5811	11321	8294	15500	21849

^aNumbers in superscript represent ranking of relative abundance.

$$N_0 = S \quad (1) \quad \text{chosen at random from a collection of } S \text{ species and } N \text{ individuals will belong.}$$

where S is the total number of species. Thus, Hill's diversity number N₁ measures the number of abundant species in a sample. H¹ is defined as

$$N_1 = e^H \quad (2) \quad H^1 = \sum_{i=1}^S (p_i / \ln p_i) \quad (4)$$

where H is Shannon's index, and

$$N_2 = 1/h \quad (3)$$

where h is Simpson's index

Shannon's index (H¹) is based on information theory. It measures the average degree of uncertainty in predicting to what species an individual

where S is the number of species and p_i is the proportion of the total number of individuals in the ith species.

Simpson's index is defined as

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^S p_i^2 \quad (5)$$